

University–Enterprise Training Linkages for Labor Market Responsiveness: A Review of International and Vietnamese Studies

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ABSTRACT: This article aims to systematize and generalize international and Vietnamese studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises in order to meet the requirements of the labor market. On the basis of analyzing and synthesizing published studies, the article clarifies the development trend of the university - enterprise relationship from the traditional training function to research collaboration, knowledge transfer, commercialization of research results, curriculum development, and human resource development. International studies show that linkages between universities and enterprises are an inevitable trend associated with the “Triple Helix model” among universities, enterprises, and the state; at the same time, they emphasize the role of strategic cooperation, mutual benefits, coordination mechanisms, and the participation of stakeholders. In the Vietnamese context, studies show that training linkages between educational institutions and enterprises have received attention but remain insufficiently close, have not yet formed sustainable cooperation mechanisms, and have not effectively connected training, scientific research, and labor demand. The article indicates that strengthening training linkages between universities and enterprises is a necessary requirement for improving training quality, developing human resources, and better meeting labor market requirements in the current context of higher education reform.

KEYWORDS: Training linkages, enterprises; labor market, human resources; higher education.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of globalization, digital transformation, and rapid changes in the labor market, higher education is facing the requirement to undergo strong reform in order to improve training quality and learners’ adaptability after graduation. The current labor market requires workers not only to possess professional knowledge but also to have practical professional competence, soft skills, adaptability, innovative thinking, and lifelong learning capacity. Therefore, universities cannot merely perform their training function in a traditional manner; instead, they need to expand relationships with enterprises, employers, and relevant stakeholders to ensure that training programs are aligned with professional practice and labor demand. Rothwell and Lindholm (1999) argue that, to improve the quality of human resource training, educational institutions need to identify and develop competencies appropriate to the requirements of the world of work. OECD (2016) emphasizes the requirement of “right jobs, right skills, right places” in human resource policy development, thereby showing that the connection between training and labor demand is an important condition for improving the effectiveness of human resource development. Training linkages between universities and enterprises constitute an important approach to narrowing the gap between training and labor utilization. In essence, this is a process of cooperation between higher education institutions and enterprises in activities such as developing training programs, organizing internships and professional practice, providing training according to enterprise needs, conducting scientific research, transferring technology, commercializing research results, and supporting employment for students after graduation. The report of the Science-to-Business Marketing Research Centre (2011) states that cooperation between higher education institutions and public and private organizations includes many forms, such as research and development cooperation, personnel exchange, commercialization of research results, development and dissemination of training programs, lifelong learning, enterprise development, and governance. Thus, university - enterprise linkages are not limited to internship or student recruitment activities, but represent a multidimensional cooperative relationship among training, research, production - business, and human resource development.

Worldwide, the relationship between universities and enterprises has been studied from various perspectives. Studies show that the role of universities has shifted from the traditional functions of teaching and research to a third function, namely serving

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socio-economic development, commercializing knowledge, and participating in the innovation ecosystem (Bonaccorsi & Piccaluga, 1994; Perkmann, 2007; Croissant & Smith-Doerr, 2008). In this trend, enterprises are no longer merely recipients of training products but have become partners participating in training, research, competency assessment, and curriculum development. The HEGESCO project also shows that cooperation between enterprises and universities plays an important role in supporting the careers of graduates, while helping higher education institutions better understand the needs of employers and the labor market (Pavlin et al., 2009). One influential theoretical framework in studies on university - enterprise cooperation is the “Triple Helix model” among universities, enterprises, and the state. According to Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz (1998, 2000), innovation and the development of the knowledge economy are formed through the interaction among three actors: universities, enterprises, and the state. In this model, universities play the role of creating knowledge, training human resources, and conducting research; enterprises apply and commercialize knowledge and provide feedback on market demand; and the state establishes mechanisms, policies, and supportive environments. This approach shows that training linkages between universities and enterprises can develop sustainably only when there is synchronous coordination among relevant stakeholders.

Mongkhonvanit (2008) also affirms that universities need to understand the needs and culture of industry, develop appropriate technology, cooperate with enterprises and the government, and build long-term strategies to improve the effectiveness of linkages. International studies indicate that linkages between universities and enterprises bring benefits to both sides. For universities, linkages with enterprises help renew training programs, improve teaching quality, increase practical opportunities for students, expand research resources, and enhance academic reputation. For enterprises, such cooperation helps them access appropriate human resources, reduce recruitment and retraining costs, exploit scientific - technological knowledge from universities, and enhance competitiveness. Rohrbeck and Arnold (2006) argue that the motivations promoting university - enterprise cooperation include improving teaching quality, seeking funding sources, accessing practical knowledge and data, responding to policy pressure, enhancing reputation, and creating employment opportunities for graduates. Rosly and Ahmad (2011) also emphasize that partnerships between universities and enterprises can only be successful and sustainable when based on mutual benefits, mutual understanding, and a long-term vision.

In Vietnam, training linkages between universities and enterprises have become a matter of concern in the context of higher education reform and improvement of human resource quality. The amended Law on Higher Education provides a legal basis for strengthening autonomy, accountability, and the connection between training and social needs. Circular No. 07/2017/TT-BGDĐT of the Ministry of Education and Training on training linkages is also an important basis for organizing coordinated training activities among educational institutions and relevant parties. From a research perspective, Phung Xuan Nha (2009) affirms the necessity of developing a training model linked to enterprise needs, in which the benefits of both educational institutions and enterprises need to be clearly identified. Studies in Vietnam also show that the linkage between universities and enterprises still has many limitations. Nguyen Duc Tri (2007) argues that the relationship between educational institutions and enterprises in Vietnam is not truly close and has not formed long-term and sustainable commitments. Tran Anh Tai (2009) observes that university training has not fully met the needs of labor users, that training has not been closely connected with labor utilization, and that linkages with enterprises often remain at the level of wishes or policies. Doan Van Tinh (2015) also points out that the relationship among institutes, universities, and enterprises in Vietnam remains limited because of administrative obstacles and financial mechanisms. These limitations hinder the improvement of training quality, university reputation, and enterprise competitiveness. Many domestic studies have approached training linkages from the perspectives of models, mechanisms, and solutions. Nguyen Van Anh (2009) emphasizes the role of enterprise relations centers in identifying and analyzing needs and managing linkage activities. Nguyen Dinh Luan (2015) proposes strengthening the management role of the state, the proactiveness of universities, enterprises’ long-term human resource development plans, and learners’ career awareness. Studies by Tran Anh Tai (2010), Le Tuan Bach and Chu Mai Linh (2015), Do The Hung et al. (2016), and Tran Sy Nguyen (2020) all agree that cooperation between universities and enterprises is an inevitable trend to reduce the gap between theory and practice, training and utilization, graduation and employment.

From the review of studies, it can be seen that training linkages between universities and enterprises are a topic of profound theoretical and practical significance. Theoretically, this topic is connected with research directions on higher education, human resource development, university governance, the innovative university model, the Triple Helix model, and training according to labor market needs. Practically, training linkages are an important pathway to improving training quality, increasing students’ employability, improving the alignment between learning outcomes and recruitment needs, and contributing to the development of high-quality human resources for the economy. However, in the Vietnamese context, studies still reveal a lack of synchronization in coordination mechanisms, limited enterprise participation in curriculum development, insufficient

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sustainability of cooperation commitments, and a gap between labor market requirements and graduates' competencies. Starting from these issues, the article "University - Enterprise Training Linkages for Labor Market Responsiveness: A Review of International and Vietnamese Studies" aims to systematize and generalize published studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises. On the basis of analyzing international and Vietnamese studies, the article clarifies the development trends of the university - enterprise relationship, typical theoretical models, benefits, barriers, and research gaps in this field. The review results contribute to providing a scientific basis for proposing research orientations and solutions to strengthen training linkages between universities and enterprises in order to improve training quality, develop human resources, and better meet labor market requirements in the current context of higher education reform.

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This article uses the literature review method to systematize, analyze, and generalize international and Vietnamese studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises in order to meet labor market requirements. This method helps identify research trends and clarify models, forms, benefits, barriers, and conditions for implementing training linkages in different contexts. The sources used include theoretical studies, scientific articles, dissertations, research projects, international reports, and domestic works related to university - enterprise cooperation, human resource development, training according to social needs, and the labor market. International documents are used to clarify the theoretical basis, cooperation models such as the Triple Helix, and trends in training linkages; meanwhile, domestic documents are used to analyze the current situation, barriers, and solution orientations in Vietnam. The analysis process is carried out according to key thematic groups: the concept and nature of training linkages; models and forms of linkages; benefits, barriers, and implementation conditions; international research trends; and the current situation and research directions in Vietnam. On that basis, the article compares, synthesizes, and generalizes research findings to identify research gaps and implications for developing training linkages between universities and enterprises.

A. International studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises

International studies show that training linkages between universities and enterprises are not a new issue; rather, they were formed quite early in the history of modern higher education. The idea of a university connected with research and social service can be seen in the university model of Wilhelm Humboldt in Germany in the early nineteenth century. According to this view, a university not only performs the function of training but must also participate in research, cooperate with industries, and contribute to social development (Humboldt, 1977). The report of the Science-to-Business Marketing Research Centre (2011) also affirms that cooperation between higher education institutions and enterprises is direct or indirect interaction between universities and public or private organizations to bring benefits to the parties, including research and development cooperation, personnel exchange, commercialization of research results, curriculum development, lifelong learning, enterprise development, and governance. This approach shows that the university - enterprise relationship has moved beyond the scope of internships or student recruitment to become a multidimensional cooperative relationship among training, research, and production - business. Along with the development of the knowledge economy, the role of universities in their relationship with enterprises has increasingly expanded. Studies by Bonaccorsi and Piccaluga (1994) and Perkmann (2007) show that modern universities no longer maintain only the two traditional functions of teaching and research, but also develop a "third function," namely commercializing knowledge, transferring technology, cooperating with enterprises, and participating in socio-economic development. In that context, enterprises are no longer merely units that use training products, but have become partners participating in training, research, curriculum development, and learner competency assessment. Croissant and Smith-Doerr (2008) also point out that the university - enterprise relationship can be examined in three dimensions: the relationship between science and the economy, the organizational relationship between universities and enterprises, and the personal relationship between scientists, lecturers, and enterprise personnel. This shows that university - enterprise linkages are a complex phenomenon with academic, organizational, and practical dimensions.

One of the typical theoretical models in studies on university - enterprise linkages is the "Triple Helix model" among universities, enterprises, and the state. According to Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz (1998, 2000), innovation and the development of the knowledge economy are formed through the interaction among three actors: universities, enterprises, and the state. In this model, universities play the role of creating knowledge, training human resources, and conducting research; enterprises play the role of applying knowledge, commercializing research results, and providing feedback on market demand; and the state plays the role of developing policies, mechanisms, and supportive environments for cooperation. Thus, training linkages between universities and enterprises are not merely a bilateral relationship between educational institutions and enterprises, but also

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require the coordinating, supporting, and orienting participation of the state. Mongkhonvanit's (2008) study of the automotive cluster in Thailand also affirms the important role of the Triple Helix model in enhancing competitiveness, in which universities need to understand the needs and culture of industry, develop appropriate technology, cooperate with enterprises and the government, and develop long-term strategies for sustainable linkage relationships.

In terms of forms and contents of linkages, international studies show that cooperation between universities and enterprises can be implemented in many different forms. Common forms include enterprise participation in developing and adjusting training programs; coordination in organizing internships and professional practice; cooperation in scientific research; technology transfer; commercialization of research results; exchange of lecturers, students, and experts; training according to enterprise needs; organization of lifelong learning; start-up support; and employment support for students after graduation (Science-to-Business Marketing Research Centre, 2011; Pavlin et al., 2009). The HEGESCO project shows that the modes of cooperation between enterprises and universities play an important role in supporting the careers of graduates, while helping universities better understand employers' needs and helping enterprises better identify graduates' competencies (Pavlin et al., 2009). This indicates that training linkages not only aim to improve training quality within universities, but also contribute to improving students' transition from the learning environment to the labor market.

International studies also affirm that linkages between universities and enterprises bring practical benefits to many stakeholders. For universities, linkages help renew training objectives, contents, and methods; improve teaching quality; expand opportunities for students' practice and internships; increase research resources; and enhance academic reputation and community service capacity. For enterprises, cooperation with universities helps them access suitable human resources, reduce recruitment and retraining costs, exploit scientific - technological knowledge, and enhance innovation capacity and competitiveness. For students, training linkages create conditions for learners to access real professional environments, develop practical skills, improve adaptability, and expand employment opportunities after graduation. At the social level, university - enterprise linkages contribute to improving the quality of human resources, promoting innovation, and better meeting socio-economic development requirements.

From the perspective of motivations and conditions for success, Rohrbeck and Arnold (2006) argue that university - enterprise cooperation is promoted by many factors such as improving teaching quality, seeking funding, accessing practical knowledge and data, responding to policy pressure, enhancing reputation, and creating employment opportunities for graduates. Rosly and Ahmad (2011) emphasize that partnerships between universities and enterprises can be successful and sustainable only when built on mutual benefits, trust, mutual understanding, clear coordination mechanisms, and a long-term vision. Similarly, Rita, Gabriela, and Anabela (2016), approaching the issue from benefits management theory, indicate that identifying benefits, success factors, and the internal characteristics of university - enterprise cooperation is an important basis for effectively forming and operating cooperative relationships. For developing countries, Guimon (2013) argues that promoting university - enterprise linkages needs to consider specific contexts, because these countries often face difficulties related to education quality, financial resources, and organizational capacity for cooperation; therefore, appropriate public policies, sufficient time, and sustained efforts are needed to build effective linkages.

In general, international studies have clarified the theoretical basis, models, forms, benefits, and conditions for developing training linkages between universities and enterprises. The general trend shows that this relationship is increasingly shifting from isolated, short-term cooperation to strategic, long-term, and multidimensional cooperation associated with innovation, human resource development, and labor market requirements. This provides an important basis for countries, including Vietnam, to consult in the process of developing training linkage models appropriate to socio-economic conditions and current requirements for higher education reform.

B. Vietnamese studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises

In Vietnam, the issue of training linkages between universities and enterprises has emerged in the context of higher education shifting from a model mainly meeting credential needs to training that meets social needs and labor market demands. Socio-economic development, the requirement to improve human resource quality, and competitive pressure in the labor market require higher education institutions to renew training objectives, contents, programs, and methods toward alignment with labor demand. Therefore, linkages between educational institutions and enterprises are not only a practical requirement but also an important approach to improving training quality, increasing students' professional adaptability, and reducing the gap between training and labor utilization. In domestic studies, Phung Xuan Nha (2009) affirms the necessity of developing a training model linked to enterprise needs in Vietnam. According to the author, this linkage brings benefits to both sides: enterprises can save costs by accessing human resources suitable for their development needs, while universities have conditions to renew training

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objectives, contents, and methods and reduce resource difficulties. However, for training linkage models to be effective, the participating parties need clear strategies, in which university autonomy and support in mechanisms, policies, and finance from the state and local authorities play important roles. In the same approach, Trinh Ngoc Thach (2017) argues that higher education development policies need to focus on strengthening linkages between universities and enterprises to create a mechanism connecting training and scientific research with production and services.

Studies in Vietnam show that training linkages between universities and enterprises have received increasing attention; however, the level of connection remains limited. Nguyen Duc Tri (2007) observes that the relationship between universities and enterprises in Vietnam is not truly close and has not created long-term and sustainable commitments. The cause of this situation is that the parties' awareness of needs, fields, and possibilities for cooperation remains insufficient; in other words, educational institutions and enterprises have not yet had substantive coordination in the process of training and using human resources. Tran Anh Tai (2009) also points out that university training has not fully met the needs of labor users; educational institutions have not truly connected with society, and training has not been closely linked with utilization. Consulting or linking with enterprises to train according to practical needs often remains at the level of policies or aspirations and has not become a regular and effective cooperation mechanism. Similarly, Doan Van Tinh (2015) argues that the relationship among institutes, universities, and enterprises in Vietnam remains quite limited and insufficiently close because of administrative obstacles and financial mechanisms. These limitations create barriers to improving training quality, university reputation, and enterprise competitiveness. Some other studies continue to affirm that linkages remain short-term and formal. Le Tuan Bach and Chu Mai Linh (2015) state that university - enterprise linkages in Vietnam have been discussed in many workshops and scientific forums, showing the importance of this issue for improving training quality. However, in practice, many linkage activities still mainly stop at organizing internships, enterprise visits, recruitment support, or short-term cooperation and have not developed into strategic partnerships. Manh Xuan (2015), through a survey of enterprises in Dong Nai, Binh Duong, and Ho Chi Minh City, also indicates that most graduates have not met enterprise requirements well; one important reason is the lack of linkages between universities and enterprises in coordinating training, assessing practical competencies, and using human resources.

Domestic studies have approached training linkages between universities and enterprises from many perspectives, such as models, mechanisms, processes, forms of organization, and solutions to improve cooperation effectiveness. Nguyen Van Anh (2009) argues that the linkage between training institutions and labor-using units is an organic and inseparable relationship; at the same time, the author proposes establishing "Enterprise Relations Centers" to analyze needs, set up appropriate forms of linkages, and manage cooperation activities in a unified manner. Nguyen Dinh Luan (2015) emphasizes the need for coordination among the state, universities, enterprises, and learners; in which the state creates supportive mechanisms, universities connect with enterprises in curriculum development, enterprises have long-term human resource development plans, and learners proactively orient their careers. In the same direction, Tran Anh Tai (2010), Do The Hung et al. (2016), and Tran Sy Nguyen (2020) have drawn on international experience to propose solutions for strengthening university - enterprise cooperation in Vietnam, aiming to narrow the gap between theory and practice and between training and labor utilization. In addition to studies at the policy and general model levels, some works focus on specific fields. Nguyen Ngoc Trung et al. (2020) study linkage models in human resource training for the tourism industry, including forms of the Triple Helix model. Nguyen Thi Hang (2013) analyzes linkage models in vocational training, such as parallel training, alternating training, and sequential training. Pham Van Thanh and Nguyen Cong Thanh (2018) emphasize the role of enterprises in training program design, regarding the training program as a "training contract" among the educational institution, learners, and enterprises, in which the participation of labor-using units is an important condition to ensure practicality. In addition, many studies propose solutions to strengthen training linkages in an application-oriented direction. Pham Thi Thuy Trang et al. (2019) affirm that university - enterprise linkages are a common trend and play an important role in ensuring the quality of students and supplying human resources for enterprises. Nguyen Minh Hien and Nguyen Hoang Lan (2014) clarify models, mechanisms, and contents of university - enterprise linkages and propose solutions to remove barriers in human resource training and research and technology development. Le Minh Phuong Mai (2020) continues to emphasize the benefits of linkages and analyzes factors affecting cooperation between universities and enterprises in application-oriented training.

Although domestic studies all affirm the necessity of training linkages between universities and enterprises, implementation practice still faces many barriers. First, the coordination mechanism among educational institutions, enterprises, and the state is not truly clear. Nguyen Dinh Luan (2015) argues that the relationship among these three actors plays an important role in forming and developing university - enterprise linkages; however, the roles, responsibilities, and benefits of each party need to be more specifically identified to avoid cooperation that is unsustainable or based only on short-term agreements. Second, enterprise

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participation in the training process remains limited. Many enterprises have not deeply participated in developing training programs, organizing practice, assessing learning outcomes, or supporting applied research. Nguyen Thi Thanh Dan (2018) shows that although 94% of surveyed enterprises have a need to cooperate with universities, the number of enterprises with specialized cooperation units remains low; cooperation activities mainly stop at managing interns or several short-term training programs. Third, barriers related to finance, administration, information, and implementation capacity still significantly affect linkage effectiveness. Doan Van Tinh (2015) points out that administrative obstacles and financial mechanisms make the relationship between universities and enterprises insufficiently close. Nguyen Duc Trong (2018) also observes that although linkage forms in technical universities have become more diverse, the level of linkage remains modest. In the tourism sector, Le Anh Tuan and Nguyen Thi Thu Hoa (2019) and Nguyen Quyet Thang and Nguyen Thi Thu Hoa (2019) state that linkage activities are influenced by factors such as organization, context, implementation, viewpoints, and linkage benefits. Fourth, the gap between graduates' competencies and employers' requirements remains a prominent issue. Pham Van Quyet and Le Chi Lan (2014) emphasize that universities need to study the requirements of labor users to adjust training programs appropriately. Nguyen Quoc Khanh and Luong Nguyen Duy Thong (2020) argue that the situation in which students have difficulty finding jobs while enterprises have difficulty recruiting suitable labor stems from obstacles in cooperation between universities and enterprises. In general, the main barriers in training linkages in Vietnam include unclear coordination mechanisms, insufficient enterprise participation, lack of resources and labor market information, formalistic linkage activities, and training programs that are not truly aligned with recruitment requirements. Therefore, for training linkages to deepen, there must be specific coordination mechanisms, substantive enterprise participation, state support, proactive renewal by universities, and an appropriate system of criteria for evaluating linkage effectiveness.

C. Comparative discussion between international and Vietnamese studies

From the review of research works, it can be seen that both international and Vietnamese studies agree that training linkages between universities and enterprises are an inevitable trend in the context in which higher education must increasingly better meet labor market requirements. International studies argue that the university - enterprise relationship not only supports internships, recruitment, or professional skills training, but also contributes to promoting research, knowledge transfer, commercialization of scientific results, and the development of the innovation ecosystem (Science-to-Business Marketing Research Centre, 2011; Bonaccorsi & Piccaluga, 1994; Perkmann, 2007). Meanwhile, Vietnamese studies also affirm that linkages between educational institutions and enterprises are an important condition for improving training quality, reducing the gap between training and labor utilization, and contributing to human resource development to meet social needs (Phung Xuan Nha, 2009; Tran Anh Tai, 2009; Nguyen Dinh Luan, 2015).

The prominent similarity between the two groups of studies is that both view enterprises not only as recipients of graduates but also as actors that need to participate in the training process. This participation can be expressed through contributing to training programs, organizing internships, supporting professional practice, participating in learner competency assessment, and coordinating in applied research. International studies emphasize that such cooperation helps universities better understand the needs of employers and helps students develop competencies appropriate to the world of work (Pavlin et al., 2009; Rohrbeck & Arnold, 2006). Similarly, in Vietnam, Pham Van Quyet and Le Chi Lan (2014) argue that universities need to study labor users' requirements to adjust training programs; Nguyen Quoc Khanh and Luong Nguyen Duy Thong (2020) also observe that obstacles in cooperation between universities and enterprises are one reason why students have difficulty finding jobs while enterprises have difficulty recruiting suitable labor.

However, there are also clear differences in approach between international and Vietnamese studies. International studies often place university - enterprise linkages within a broader theoretical framework of the knowledge economy, innovation, and modern university governance. A typical example is the Triple Helix model of Leydesdorff and Etzkowitz (1998, 2000), in which universities, enterprises, and the state are viewed as three interacting actors that promote innovation and socio-economic development. According to this approach, training linkages are not only a bilateral relationship between educational institutions and enterprises, but also require the coordinating, supporting, and policy-creating role of the state. Studies such as those of Mongkhonvanit (2008), Rosly and Ahmad (2011), and Guimon (2013) also emphasize long-term strategy, mutual benefits, trust, and sustainable coordination mechanisms in developing university - enterprise relationships. In contrast, studies in Vietnam mainly focus on analyzing the current situation, identifying barriers, and proposing solutions to enhance the effectiveness of training linkages. Nguyen Duc Tri (2007) and Tran Anh Tai (2009) point out that the relationship between universities and enterprises in Vietnam remains insufficiently close, that training is not linked to utilization, and that it has not fully met labor users' needs. Doan Van Tinh (2015) emphasizes administrative and financial obstacles; Nguyen Duc Trong (2018) argues that although

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linkage forms in technical universities have become more diverse, the level of linkage remains modest. Some other studies propose specific models or solutions, such as establishing enterprise relations centers (Nguyen Van Anh, 2009), strengthening the roles of the state, universities, enterprises, and learners (Nguyen Dinh Luan, 2015), or applying linkage models in specific fields such as tourism, vocational education, and application-oriented training (Nguyen Thi Hang, 2013; Nguyen Ngoc Trung et al., 2020; Le Minh Phuong Mai, 2020). This difference shows that international studies have developed toward deeper theorization and systematization of university - enterprise linkages, viewing them as part of the innovation ecosystem and the development of the knowledge economy. Meanwhile, studies in Vietnam still tend to be practice-oriented, focusing on issues such as the lack of coordination mechanisms, lack of long-term commitments, insufficient enterprise participation in the training process, training programs that are not aligned with recruitment requirements, and graduates who have not adequately met labor market demands. This reflects the Vietnamese context, where training linkages have been recognized as necessary but have not truly developed into strategic, sustainable cooperation relationships with clear mechanisms for effectiveness evaluation.

In general, the comparison between international and Vietnamese studies shows that training linkages between universities and enterprises are a topic of clear theoretical and practical value. International studies provide theoretical foundations, models, and experience in developing strategic cooperative relationships, while Vietnamese studies clearly reflect needs, current situations, and barriers in implementation. Therefore, future research in Vietnam needs to move from affirming necessity and describing the current situation toward developing appropriate linkage models, creating tools to evaluate linkage effectiveness, and verifying the impact of training linkages on human resource quality and labor market responsiveness.

D. Research gaps and implications for Vietnam

From the review of international and Vietnamese studies, it can be seen that training linkages between universities and enterprises have been affirmed as an inevitable trend to improve the quality of higher education, develop human resources, and meet labor market requirements. International studies have approached this issue on a relatively clear theoretical foundation, especially the Triple Helix model among universities, enterprises, and the state, which emphasizes the interaction of the three actors in the development of the knowledge economy, innovation, and knowledge commercialization (Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1998, 2000). Meanwhile, studies in Vietnam have pointed out the necessity of training linkages while clarifying many limitations such as insufficiently close coordination mechanisms, limited enterprise participation in the training process, short-term cooperation activities, and a lack of sustainability (Phung Xuan Nha, 2009; Nguyen Duc Tri, 2007; Tran Anh Tai, 2009; Doan Van Tinh, 2015).

First, a notable research gap is the need to further study the tripartite coordination mechanism among universities, enterprises, and the state. The Triple Helix model shows that training linkages cannot be viewed only as a bilateral relationship between educational institutions and enterprises; they also require the state's role in creating, coordinating, and supporting policies (Leydesdorff & Etzkowitz, 1998, 2000). In the Vietnamese context, Nguyen Dinh Luan (2015) also emphasizes the role of the state, universities, enterprises, and learners in forming sustainable linkages. However, current studies have not yet fully clarified the responsibilities, benefits, operating mechanisms, and specific modes of coordination among these three actors. Therefore, future studies need to focus on developing tripartite linkage governance models appropriate to Vietnamese higher education, clearly identifying the state's role in policy-making, the university's role in organizing training, and the enterprise's role in providing feedback on labor market needs.

Second, it is necessary to develop training linkage models appropriate to each occupational field and the conditions of each locality. Domestic studies have initially mentioned several linkage models, such as enterprise relations centers, parallel training, alternating training, sequential training, linkage models in tourism human resource training, and cooperation models in technical universities (Nguyen Van Anh, 2009; Nguyen Thi Hang, 2013; Nguyen Ngoc Trung et al., 2020; Nguyen Duc Trong, 2018). However, these models still need to be further tested, adjusted, and developed according to the characteristics of each profession, type of university, enterprise capacity, and local socio-economic conditions. The implication is that Vietnam should not mechanically apply international models, but should develop flexible linkage models capable of adapting to different fields such as engineering, tourism, economics, services, technology, vocational education, and application-oriented training programs.

Third, more empirical studies are needed to evaluate the impact of training linkages on training quality, professional skills, and students' employability. Many studies in Vietnam have pointed out that graduates have not adequately met enterprise requirements, training programs are not closely linked with professional practice, and universities do not yet have adequate mechanisms to measure learners' professional adaptability after graduation (Tran Anh Tai, 2009; Manh Xuan, 2015; Pham Van Quyet & Le Chi Lan, 2014). However, there is still a lack of quantitative or mixed-method studies that directly measure the impact of specific forms of linkages, such as internships at enterprises, enterprise participation in curriculum development, co-supervision

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of projects, order-based training, or outcome competency assessment. Therefore, future studies need to use empirical data to determine which linkage forms have the strongest impact on professional competence, employability, and students' adaptation to the labor market.

Fourth, it is necessary to develop a set of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of training linkages between universities and enterprises. At present, many studies have addressed the benefits, conditions, and barriers of linkages, but have not established a unified system of criteria for evaluating the level and quality of cooperation. Nguyen Duc Trong (2018) argues that the forms of linkages between technical universities and enterprises in Vietnam are quite diverse, but the level of linkage remains modest; meanwhile, Le Anh Tuan and Nguyen Thi Thu Hoa (2019) and Nguyen Quyet Thang and Nguyen Thi Thu Hoa (2019) point out factors affecting training linkages in the tourism sector, such as organization, context, implementation, viewpoints, and linkage benefits. These results suggest the need to develop a set of criteria capable of measuring dimensions such as the level of enterprise participation, regularity of cooperation, degree of alignment between training programs and recruitment needs, effectiveness of internships and practice, enterprise satisfaction, students' professional competence, and employment outcomes after graduation.

Fifth, it is necessary to promote the substantive participation of enterprises in the entire training process. Studies show that many linkage activities in Vietnam still mainly stop at managing student internships, recruitment, enterprise visits, or short-term training programs. Nguyen Thi Thanh Dan (2018) points out that although many enterprises need to cooperate with universities, the number of enterprises with specialized cooperation units remains low and cooperation activities have not truly deepened. Pham Van Thanh and Nguyen Cong Thanh (2018) emphasize that training programs need to be developed with the participation of relevant stakeholders, especially labor-using units. Therefore, an important implication is to shift enterprises from the role of "recipients of training products" to the role of "co-creators of the training process" through participation in curriculum development, organization of professional practice, assessment of learning outcomes, support for applied research, co-supervision of students, and creation of employment opportunities after graduation.

Research gaps in Vietnam are not limited to the lack of appropriate linkage models, but also include the lack of tripartite coordination mechanisms, tools for evaluating linkage effectiveness, and empirical evidence on the impact of training linkages on learners and the labor market. Therefore, future studies need to move from describing the current situation and proposing general solutions toward developing models, testing models, and evaluating the impact of training linkages using specific data. In practical terms, universities need to proactively establish strategic partnerships with enterprises; enterprises need to participate more deeply in the training process; and the state needs to complete mechanisms, policies, and supportive resources. These are important conditions for training linkages between universities and enterprises in Vietnam to develop in a substantive and sustainable manner and better meet labor market requirements in the context of higher education reform.

III. CONCLUSION

This article has systematized and generalized international and Vietnamese studies on training linkages between universities and enterprises in order to meet labor market requirements. On the basis of reviewing published studies, the article clarifies the development of the university - enterprise relationship from the traditional training function to a multidimensional cooperation model, including the development and adjustment of training programs, organization of practice and internships, coordination in scientific research, knowledge transfer, commercialization of research results, human resource development, and employment support for students after graduation. Accordingly, training linkages are not merely viewed as an activity supporting recruitment or internships, but as an important method for renewing higher education, narrowing the gap between training and labor utilization, improving human resource quality, and increasing students' professional adaptability in the context of a rapidly changing labor market.

The review results show that international studies often approach university - enterprise linkages as part of the innovation ecosystem, associated with strategic cooperation models, the Triple Helix model among universities - enterprises - the state, mutual benefits, trust, and sustainable coordination mechanisms. In these studies, enterprises are not only recipients of training products but also partners participating in the training process, research, curriculum development, and learner competency assessment. Meanwhile, Vietnamese studies show that training linkages between universities and enterprises have received increasing attention, especially in the context of higher education reform and the requirement that training meet social needs. However, linkage activities still have several limitations, such as unclear coordination mechanisms, insufficiently defined roles of stakeholders, limited enterprise participation in the training process, short-term cooperation activities, lack of sustainable commitments, and ineffective connection among training, scientific research, and labor demand.

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From the research results, it can be affirmed that strengthening training linkages between universities and enterprises is a necessary requirement for improving training quality, developing students' professional competencies, and better meeting labor market requirements. For linkages to become substantive and sustainable, close coordination among universities, enterprises, and the state is required. Universities need to proactively renew programs, training methods, and cooperation mechanisms; enterprises need to participate more deeply in curriculum development, practice organization, outcome competency assessment, and employment support; and the state needs to create favorable mechanisms, policies, and environments for cooperation. At the same time, future studies should focus on testing the effectiveness of linkage models in specific fields and localities, developing criteria for evaluating linkage quality, and measuring the impact of training linkages on students' professional competencies, employability, and adaptability after graduation. This provides an important basis for promoting university - enterprise training linkages in Vietnam in a substantive and effective manner that is consistent with human resource development requirements in the current period.

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